

Paper 5

**A STUDY ON THE ATTITUDE OF STUDENT TEACHERS STUDYING
UNDER MANGALORE UNIVERSITY TOWARDS TEACHER
ELIGIBILITY TEST (TET)**

Santhosh Albert Saldanha

Research scholar, Department of Education, Srinivas University Mangalore

Email: santhosh.saldanha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Teacher Eligibility Test (TET) has become one of the essential qualifications for securing a government job in any of the primary and the high schools in Karnataka. NCTE through its notification dated Feb 11, 2011 has cleared the detail guidelines and conditions for examination. The purpose of the study is to find out the attitudes of student teachers towards Teacher Eligibility Test (TET). A sample of 78 student-teachers studying in different B.Ed. colleges affiliated Mangalore University, Mangalore participated in this study. The result of the study indicated that the students belongs to urban areas have positive attitude towards TET than rural areas students. So it is suggested that the required orientation, resources, training, and facilities should be given to the student teachers during their training to achieve educational goals.

KEYWORDS Attitude, student-Teachers, Teacher Eligibility Test

INTRODUCTION

Education is a process of acquiring knowledge and skills in general and in the field of teacher’s education. Quality teacher’s education is the need of the day. The effective teaching depends upon the teacher with latest knowledge, skills and technology. It is necessary to ensure teachers with the aptitude and ability to meet the challenges of teaching at the primary and high school. Having a degree with teacher education like D.Ed. or B.Ed. is not enough to become a school teacher. So the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) recommended introducing Teacher Eligibility Test (TET) to check the entry behavior of the teachers. It is conducted by both Central and State governments in India. Most states conduct their own TET. The NCERT has

decided to improve the quality in teacher education by conducting CTET and it recommends to state governments to conduct the eligibility test at state. TETs should be made mandatory for teacher recruitment throughout the country at all levels of school education. Teachers could be required to renew their certifications periodically so that they continue to study in their own development. This study is intended to know the attitude of the student-teachers towards TET examination.

The Teacher Eligibility Test (TET) which will be conducted by the appropriate Government. The rationale for including the TET as a minimum qualification for a person to be eligible for appointment is as under. It would bring national standards of teacher quality in the recruitment process. It would induce teacher education institutions and students for these institutions to further improve their standards. The TET examination may be conducted by the suitable professional body designated by the appropriate Government for the purpose. It will be conducted in accordance with the Guidelines

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The NCERT has decided to improve the quality in teacher education by Conducting CTET and it recommends to state governments to conduct the eligibility test at state. The primary aim of CTET and TET are to make quality teacher education and reducing the jobless teachers. This study is used to know the attitude of the student teachers towards TET examination. So, the investigator of the study has taken the topic as ‘A study on the attitude of student teachers Studying under Mangalore University towards Teacher Eligibility Test (TET)’

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find out the significant difference between the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their Gender.
- To find out the significant difference between the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their locality.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY.

- There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards TET with respect to their Gender

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- There is no significant difference among the attitude of B.Ed. student-teachers towards Teacher Eligibility Test with respect to their locality.

METHODOLOGY

The study is based on descriptive survey method. The sample consists of 78 students teachers studying in different B. Ed colleges affiliated to Mangalore University, Mangalore. A tool like ‘Attitude towards TET’ is used to measure the attitude of student’s teacher which was constructed by the investigator.

SAMPLE

The investigator used convenient sampling technique in non-probability sampling technique and chosen as many as 78 B.Ed. student-teachers in Mangalore University, Mangalore. TOOL In the present study the investigator has constructed. The tool was framed as liker type scale and each statement is set against a five-point scale of “strongly agree”, “agree”, “neutral”, “disagree”, “strongly disagree” and the scoring response for positive statements is 5,4,3,2,1 and scoring is reversed for negative statements. The final tool consists of 15statements and all statements are favorable to the variable or study.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The data was collected by the investigator using the tool developed for this purpose. All the data were collected by the investigator using GOOGLE form by sending GOOGLE Link <https://forms.gle/wbQHLQh5pLjFdECRA>

Table-1

Significance of difference between boys and girls students teacher on attitude towards TET

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	Level of Significance
Attitude Towards TET	Boys	6	7.31	6.30	3.822	Not Significant at 0.05 level
	Girls	72	45.88	7.17		

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It is shown from the Table-1 that the mean scores of boys and girls student teacher on attitude towards TET are 7.31 and 45.88 with SD's 6.30 and 7.17 respectively. The t-ratio comes out to be 3.88, which is not significant at any level of significance. That means there are no significant differences in attitude between boys and girls student teacher towards TET. However the mean score of girls' student teacher is higher than the boys' students. It implies that the girl's students have some extent positive attitude towards TET.

Table-2

Significance of difference between urban and rural students

Teachers on attitude towards TET

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	Level of Significance
Attitude Towards TET	Rural	51	47.08	7.17	1.659	Significant at 0.05 level
	Urban	27	44.5	6.30		

It is shown from the Table-2 that the mean scores of rural and urban student- teachers on attitude towards TET are 47.08 and 44.5 with SD's 7.17 and 6.30 respectively. The t-ratio comes out to be 1.659, which is significant at 0.05 levels. That means there is a significant difference between rural and urban student teacher on attitude towards TET. Further, the mean scores of urban students are higher than the rural. It indicates that students teachers belong to urban areas have positive attitude towards TET as compare to their counter parts.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The teachers have a significant role to enhance the quality education at school and high school level. The appointments of teachers are also taken into consideration seriously and fairly. The teachers who have passion and skill to teach should be appointed. So the govt. takes initiative to check the competence and skills of prospective teachers. The findings of the study revealed that student teachers are having positive attitude towards TET. So some motivation program and orientation should be given to the students to pursue and have created interest towards TET. Further, the urban students have positive attitude towards TET as compare to their rural students.

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There should be created awareness program about need and importance of TET to become teachers. So, teachers should be prepared and should always be at their best for enhancing attitude towards TET. Most of the student teachers strongly agree for the TET.

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